

CACHE 1 – LRRK2_WDR

Participant 1179

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1179_36
 KD LRRK2 129µM – 78% binding
 KD NSD2 – NA – 24% binding
 100% solub /no agg. at 200 µM

Aggregation/solubility measured by DLS

Compound Name	Normalized Intensity (kCnt/s)			Laser Power (%)		
	200µM	100µM	50µM	200µM	100µM	50µM
2% DMSO control	487	827	1595	100	100	100
CACHE-HO_1179_1	845	1166	1258	100	100	100
CACHE-HO_1179_10	1052	428	546	100	100	100
CACHE-HO_1179_2	1415	1125	842	100	100	100
CACHE-HO_1179_44	804	938	1251	93	100	100
CACHE-HO_1179_6	3832	774	897	60	100	100
CACHE-HO_1179_7	1647	1327	532	73	100	100

33 analogs of chemotype 1 submitted in round 2. 6 of these show dose-response binding by SPR; one is a resupply of the original hit CACHE_1179_36.

Lacks orthogonal confirmation by a second experimental method. CACHE_HO_1179_1 destabilizes the target instead of stabilizing it (DSF experiment)

CACHE_HO_1179_7

KD LRRK2 47µM – 25% binding
 Sol/agg ok at 100 uM; sol/agg compromised at 200 uM

CACHE_HO_1179_2

KD LRRK2 21µM – 17% binding
 solub /agg. Ok at 200 µM

CACHE_HO_1179_1

KD LRRK2 73µM – 59% binding
 ITC – did not confirm
 DSF: dT -0.9; -1.3; -4.6 @ 100;200.500 µM
 solub /agg. OK at 200 µM

CACHE_HO_1179_6

KD LRRK2 4µM – 18% binding
 Sol/agg ok at 100 uM; sol/agg compromised at 200 uM

CACHE_HO_1179_10

KD LRRK2 21µM – 15% binding
 solub /agg. Ok at 200 µM

CACHE_HO_1179_44

KD LRRK2 47µM – 39% binding
 ITC – did not confirm
 Solub / agg. OK at 200 µM

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1179_94
 KD LRRK2 22uM; 45% binding
 NSD2 – 28% binding KD not determined
 Aggregates, not soluble at 100 μM

6 analogs of chemotype 2 were submitted in round 2. One is a resupply of the hit CACHE_1179_94. The resupply is more soluble and aggregates less.

Compounds are not confirmed by DSF (compounds do not stabilize LRRK2).

Aggregation/solubility measured by DLS

Compound Name	Normalized Intensity (kCnt/s)			Laser Power (%)		
	200μM	100μM	50μM	200μM	100μM	50μM
2% DMSO control	487	827	1595	100	100	100
CACHE-HO_1179_41	1334	1127	1697	100	100	100
CACHE-HO_1179_45	1506	1870	2892	100	100	100

CACHE-HO_1179_45
 KD LRRK2 13uM – 67%

DSF – did not confirm

Sol ok at 200uM; agg may be compromised from as low as 50 uM; strange trend of agg with concentration

CACHE_HO_1179_41

KD LRRK2 >200μM (396 uM)– 115% binding

DSF – did not confirm

Sol ok at 200uM; strange trend of agg with concentration

CACHE 1 – LRRK2_WDR

Participant 1181

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1181_33
 KD LRRK2 123µM – 100% binding
 KD NSD2 – NA – 41% binding
 25% solub / agg. at 200 µM

CACHE_HO_1181_24
 KD LRRK2 56µM – 30% binding
19F-NMR – confirms binding
 Sol / agg. OK at 200 µM

CACHE_HO_1181_24
 Crystal trials

CACHE_1181_33 had 31 analogs submitted in round 2. Of these one confirms by 19F-NMR.

Aggregation/solubility measured by DLS

Compound Name	Normalized Intensity (kCnt/s)			Laser Power (%)		
	200µM	100µM	50µM	200µM	100µM	50µM
2% DMSO control	487	827	1595	100	100	100
CACHE-HO_1181_12	840	7770	1300	100	100	100
CACHE-HO_1181_2	3344	6792	7377	100	100	100
CACHE-HO_1181_24	740	1465	1654	100	100	100
CACHE-HO_1181_29	1720	2216	3239	100	100	95
CACHE-HO_1181_30	3788	2230	1398	68	100	100
CACHE-HO_1181_33	985	1115	2104	100	100	100
CACHE-HO_1181_9	2206	676	2151	100	100	100

CACHE-HO_1181_30
 >200uM (544uM)– 50% binding
 Sol/agg compromised at 200 uM

CACHE-HO_1181_9
 >200 uM (622 uM) – 74% binding
 Sol ok to 200 uM; agg could be an issue from 50-200 uM because it does not trend with concentration

CACHE-HO_1181_33
 KD LRRK2 >200 uM (246 uM)– 38% binding
 DSF – did not confirm
 solub / agg ok at 200 uM

CACHE_HO_1181_2
 KD LRRK2 155µM – 29% binding
 Sol ok at 200 µM; agg likely from as low as 50 uM

CACHE-HO_1181_29
 (same as 1181_33)
 KD >200uM (310uM)– 76% binding
 Sol ok at 200 uM; agg could be an issue from as low as 50 uM
 DSF – does not confirm

CACHE_HO_1181_12
 KD LRRK2 4µM – 15% binding
 Sol OK at 200 µM; agg has a strange trend

CACHE_1181_50 = CACHE-HO_1181_34
Both confirmed by 19F-NMR.

No analogs were submitted in round 2.

Aggregation/solubility measured by DLS

Compound Name	Normalized Intensity (kCnt/s)			Laser Power (%)		
	200µM	100µM	50µM	200µM	100µM	50µM
2% DMSO control	487	827	1595	100	100	100
CACHE-HO_1181_34	893	644	603	100	100	100

CACHE-HO_1181_34
147uM – 71% binding
Sol/agg ok at 200 uM
19F-NMR – binding confirmed
DSF – did not confirm

NA – did not yield usable/binding data

CACHE 1 – LRRK2_WDR

Participant 1183

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1183_25
 KD LRRK2 16µM – 79%
 binding
 KD NSD2 – NA – 49% binding
 ~30% solub / agg. at 200 µM

CACHE_HO_1183_19
 KD LRRK2 18µM – 80% binding
DSF: 1.1 at 200 µM; 0.7 at 100 µM
 Sol /agg ok to 200 µM

43 analogs submitted in round 2.
 Six analogs show dose-response binding by SPR;
 one additionally confirms by DSF.

CACHE_HO_1183_47
 KD LRRK2 34µM – 80% binding
 DSF – did not confirm
 solub /agg. OK at 200 µM

CACHE_HO_1183_41
 KD LRRK2 44µM – 85% binding
 Sol/agg compromised at 200 µM
 DSF – did not confirm

CACHE_HO_1183_46
 KD LRRK2 41µM – 71% binding
 Sol/agg compromised at 200 µM
 DSF: 0.6 at 100µM; -0.3 at 200µM
 but sol. Issues at 200 µM

CACHE_HO_1183_13
 KD LRRK2 5µM – 40% binding
 DSF – did not confirm
 Sol/agg compromised from as low as 100 µM

CACHE_HO_1183_16
 KD LRRK2 3µM – 31% binding
 Agg ok. to 200 µM; sol starts to be
 compromised at 100 µM
 DSF – did not confirm

Aggregation/solubility measured by DLS

Compound Name	Normalized Intensity (kCnt/s)			Laser Power (%)		
	200µM	100µM	50µM	200µM	100µM	50µM
2% DMSO control	487	827	1595	100	100	100
CACHE-HO_1183_13	1336	2895	2688	83	75	100
CACHE-HO_1183_16	789	718	1155	85	95	100
CACHE-HO_1183_19	1781	1381	1054	100	100	100
CACHE-HO_1183_41	4253	1564	1248	65	100	100
CACHE-HO_1183_46	2855	1108	1619	68	100	100
CACHE-HO_1183_47	1051	1040	769	100	100	100

NA – did not yield usable/binding data

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1183_2
 KD LRRK2 32 μ M – 68% binding
 KD NSD2 42 μ M – 43% binding

4 analogs submitted in round 2 with one showing dose-response binding by SPR.

Parent molecule binds an unrelated target: NSD2-PWWP1 domain

CACHE_HO_1183_4

KD LRRK2 >200 μ M (370 μ M) – 41% binding

Sol/agg ok to 200 μ M

Compound Name	Normalized Intensity (kCnt/s)			Laser Power (%)		
	200 μ M	100 μ M	50 μ M	200 μ M	100 μ M	50 μ M
2% DMSO control	487	827	1595	100	100	100
CACHE-HO_1183_4	1020	434	905	100	100	100

Cache-HO_1183_4; LRRK2; 1:1 binding

CACHE 1 – LRRK2_WDR

Participant 1184

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1184_17
LRRK2 145 uM – 120% binding
NSD2 185% binding

10 analogs submitted in round 2. One has dose-response binding by SPR.
Solubility and aggregation look good up to 200 μM.

No orthogonal confirmation of compounds.

CACHE_HO-1184_24
SPR >200μM (260uM) – 53% binding
Sol/agg fine up to 200 uM
DSF – did not confirm

Aggregation/solubility measured by DLS

Compound Name	Normalized Intensity (kCnt/s)			Laser Power (%)		
	200μM	100μM	50μM	200μM	100μM	50μM
2% DMSO control	487	827	1595	100	100	100
CACHE-HO_1184_24	873	741	1009	100	100	100

CACHE 1 – LRRK2_WDR

Participant 1186

PARENT MOLECULES

CACHE_1186_2
 SPR LRRK2 26 μM – 90% binding
 SPR NSD2 46 μM – 67% binding
 ITC – 38 μM

Parent molecule binds unrelated target (NSD2-PWWP1)
 17 compounds submitted in round 2.
 Two compounds show dose-response binding by SPR.

Aggregation/solubility measured by DLS

Compound Name	Normalized Intensity (kCnt/s)			Laser Power (%)		
	200 μM	100 μM	50 μM	200 μM	100 μM	50 μM
2% DMSO control	487	827	1595	100	100	100
CACHE-HO_1186_1	1018	1000	1141	98	100	100
CACHE-HO_1186_38	578	1572	701	100	100	100
CACHE-HO_1186_39	1237	1024	1533	83	100	100

CACHE_HO_1186_38
 SPR >200 μM (364 μM) – 57% binding
 DSF – not tested; ITC – no binding

CACHE_HO_1186_39
 SPR 212 μM – 49% binding
 DSF – not tested; ITC – no binding

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1186_85
 KD LRRK2 53µM – 75% binding
 KD NSD2 – 138 µM – 60% binding
 solub / agg. OK at 200 µM

Aggregation/solubility measured by DLS

Compound Name	Normalized Intensity (kCnt/s)			Laser Power (%)		
	200µM	100µM	50µM	200µM	100µM	50µM
2% DMSO control	487	827	1595	100	100	100
CACHE-HO_1186_1	1018	1000	1141	98	100	100

Parent molecule binds NSD2-PWWP1

8 analogs were submitted in round 2.
 Only the resupplied compound shows binding in dose-response by SPR. It does not confirm by DSF.

CACHE_HO_1186_1
 SPR 45 µM – 39% binding
 DSF – not tested

CACHE 1 – LRRK2_WDR

Participant 1187

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1187_84
 SPR 55 μ M, 36% binding
 SPR – NSD2 13% binding
 NMR – did not confirm

7 analogs submitted in round 2. two show dose-response binding by SPR.

One confirms by 19F-NMR.

CACHE_HO-1187_17
 SPR >200 μ M (459 μ M) – 43% binding
 Sol/agg ok to only to 100 μ M
 DSF – does not confirm
 19F NMR: does not confirm

19F-NMR

CACHE-HO_1187_30
 SPR 93 μ M – 34% binding;
19F-NMR – shows binding
 Sol/agg good to 200 μ M

19F-NMR

Black: 10 μ M compound
 Red: 10 μ M compound + 20 μ M protein

Aggregation/solubility measured by DLS

Compound Name	Normalized Intensity (kCnt/s)			Laser Power (%)		
	200 μ M	100 μ M	50 μ M	200 μ M	100 μ M	50 μ M
2% DMSO control	487	827	1595	100	100	100
CACHE-HO_1187_17	8853	2519	1512	58	78	100
CACHE-HO_1187_18	608	1373	651	100	100	100
CACHE-HO_1187_19	657	431	604	100	100	100
CACHE-HO_1187_20	566	1066	858	100	100	100
CACHE-HO_1187_30	1466	1753	649	100	100	100

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1187_74
 SPR LRRK2 42 uM – 41% binding
 SPR NSD2 – 32% binding

9 compounds submitted in round 2.

1 binds weakly in dose-response in SPR at concentration where solubility is poor

Aggregation/solubility measured by DLS

Compound Name	Normalized Intensity (kCnt/s)			Laser Power (%)		
	200µM	100µM	50µM	200µM	100µM	50µM
2% DMSO control	487	827	1595	100	100	100
CACHE-HO_1187_36	4091	1544	1001	58	100	100

CACHE_HO_1187_36
 SPR >200µM (600 uM) – 81% binding
 Sol/agg is compromised at 200 uM
 DSF – no binding

PARENT MOLECULES (no analog in Round 2)

CACHE_1187_28
 SPR LRRK2 no KD reported – 32% binding
 SPR NSD2 – 14% binding
19F NMR – Yes in DR

Common Name	K _D (μM)	Binding activity%	Comment
CACHE_1187_28	-	32	Low signal

CACHE_1187_59
 SPR LRRK2 25uM – 64% binding
 SPR NSD2 – 22% binding

Common Name	K _D (μM)	Binding activity%	Comment
CACHE_1187_59	25	64	

confirmed by 19F-NMR

¹⁹F-NMR

Black: 10 μM compound
 Red: 10 μM compound + 10 μM protein
 Green: 10 μM compound + 20 μM protein

Aggregation/solubility measured by DLS

Compound Name	Solubility (% Laser Power)						Aggregation (Intensity - kCnt/s)					
	12.5μM	25μM	50μM	100μM	150μM	200μM	12.5μM	25μM	50μM	100μM	150μM	200μM
CACHE_1187_59	98	100	95	100	100	98	926	557	1366	1005	1827	914
CACHE_1187_28	100	100	100	55	75	20	546	402	444	1703	1319	27594

CACHE 1 – LRRK2_WDR

Participant 1188

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1188_92
 KD LRRK2 18µM – 46% binding
 KD NSD2 – NA – 37% binding
 DSF does not confirm binding
 ~55% solub / agg. at 200 µM

Aggregation/solubility measured by DLS

Compound Name	Normalized Intensity (kCnt/s)				Laser Power (%)			
	500 µM	200µM	100µM	50µM	500 µM	200µM	100µM	50µM
2% DMSO control		487	827	1595	100	100	100	100
CACHE-HO_1188_1		1269	1998	792	100	100	100	100
CACHE-HO_1188_30		1736	659	821	100	100	100	100
CACHE-HO_1188_33		1223	896	825	100	100	100	100
CACHE-HO_1188_36		1237	504	648	100	100	100	100
CACHE-HO_1188_37		1115	498	1140	100	100	100	100
CACHE-HO_1188_38		619	662	849	100	98	100	100
CACHE-HO_1188_41	1150	361	412	466	98	100	100	100
CACHE-HO_1188_48		619	867	986	100	100	100	100

20 analogs submitted in round 2.

Four show dose-response binding by SPR.

CACHE_HO_1188_41 appears to confirm by DSF.

CACHE_HO_1188_30
 KD LRRK2 169µM – 23% binding
 Solub / agg. Ok to 200 µM
 DSF – does not confirm

CACHE_HO_1188_38
 KD LRRK2 61µM – 50% binding
 Solub / agg. Ok to 200 µM
 DSF – does not confirm

CACHE_HO_1188_41
 KD LRRK2 150µM – 74% binding
 DSF – dT 0.8;0.4;1C @ 100;200;500uM
 Solub / agg. Ok to 500 µM

CACHE_HO_1188_36
 KD LRRK2 22µM – 29% binding
 ITC – did not confirm
 DSF – does not confirm
 Solub /agg. Ok to 200 µM

13 analogs submitted in round 2.
 Only the resupplied parent compound shows
 weak dose-response binding by SPR.

CACHE-HO_1188_48
 SPR 207uM – 65% binding
 Sol/agg good to 200 uM

Aggregation/solubility measured by DLS

Compound Name	Normalized Intensity (kCnt/s)			Laser Power (%)		
	200µM	100µM	50µM	200µM	100µM	50µM
2% DMSO control	487	827	1595	100	100	100
CACHE-HO_1188_48	619	867	986	100	100	100

CACHE 1 – LRRK2_WDR

Participant 1193

CACHE_1193_8
 SPR LRRK2 97 μ M – 84% binding
 SPR NSD2 – NA – 37% binding
 19F – binding not confirmed

CACHE_HO_1193_25
 KD LRRK2 >200 uM (500 μ M) – 63% binding
DSF – appears to confirm binding
 19F-NMR – binding not confirmed
 Solub / agg. Good to 200 μ M

Compound Name	Δ Tm	200 μ M	100 μ M
CACHE-HO_1193_25		1.7	1.3

CACHE_HO_1193_21
 KD LRRK2 >200uM (436 μ M) – 100% binding
 19F-NMR – binding not confirmed
 Sol good to 100 uM, Agg. Good to 200 μ M

Same series as CACHE_1193_26

7 analogs submitted in round 2.

Two analogs shows dose-response binding but affinities are > 200 uM.

19F-NMR does not confirm binding.

DSF appears to show binding. There is no concentration dependence of binding.

19F NMR

Aggregation/solubility measured by DLS

Compound Name	Normalized Intensity (kCnt/s)			Laser Power (%)		
	200 μ M	100 μ M	50 μ M	200 μ M	100 μ M	50 μ M
2% DMSO control	487	827	1595	100	100	100
CACHE-HO_1193_21	5156	1614	1690	65	100	100
CACHE-HO_1193_25	1407	2855	1504	100	100	100

19F NMR

CACHE 1 – LRRK2_WDR

Participant 1195

PARENT MOLECULES

CACHE_1195_6
 KD LRRK2 117µM – 100% binding
 KD NSD2 – NA – 25% binding
 ITC: ??; **19F NMR: binds**
 100% solub / no agg. at 200 µM

CACHE_1195_32
 KD LRRK2 113 µM – 64% binding
 NSD2: linear
 100% solb / sign of aggreg at 100 µM

7 analogs submitted in round 2.
 Parent molecule resupply confirmed by NMR
 3 analogs confirm by dose-response SPR; 1 appears to confirm by DSF

CACHE-HO_1195_22
 KD 220uM - 88 % binding
 DSF – does not confirm
 Sol/agg ok up to 100 uM; *compromised at 200 uM*

CACHE_HO_1195_36
 KD LRRK2 240µM – 100% binding
DSF – 1.3 at 200 uM
 Solub / agg. Good to 200 µM

Compound Name	ΔTm	200µM	100µM
CACHE-HO_1195_36		1.3	0.3

CACHE_HO_1195_35
 KD LRRK2 180µM – 103% binding
 DSF – does not confirm
 Sol/agg good to 100 uM; *compromised at 200 uM*

Aggregation/solubility measured by DLS

Compound Name	Normalized Intensity (kCnt/s)			Laser Power (%)		
	200µM	100µM	50µM	200µM	100µM	50µM
2% DMSO control	487	827	1595	100	100	100
CACHE-HO_1195_22	2275	963	506	60	100	100
CACHE-HO_1195_35	4169	1440	727	68	100	100
CACHE-HO_1195_36	1083	920	1140	100	100	100

CACHE_1195_43

KD LRRK2 141 μM – 48% binding
 KD NSD2 linear, 63% binding
 Sol ok at 500 μM but aggregation is a problem (15K counts/s in duplicate samples)

CACHE_HO_1195_37

KD LRRK2 54 μM – 98% binding
 Sol good to 200 μM ; *agg may be compromised from as low as 50 μM*
 DSF – did not confirm

Same series as CACHE_1195_6

11 analogs submitted in round 2.

Two have dose-response binding by SPR.

One confirms by 19F NMR

CACHE_HO_1195_17

KD LRRK2 39 μM – 34% binding
19F-NMR – confirms binding
 Solub / agg. Good to 200 μM

Aggregation/solubility measured by DLS

Compound Name	Normalized Intensity (kCnt/s)			Laser Power (%)		
	200 μM	100 μM	50 μM	200 μM	100 μM	50 μM
2% DMSO control	487	827	1595	100	100	100
CACHE-HO_1195_17	986	965	936	100	100	100
CACHE-HO_1195_37	1882	1439	1425	100	100	100

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1195_60

KD LRRK2 44µM – 48% binding

KD NSD2 – NA – 46% binding

ITC: seems to bind

Poor solubility and aggregation at 500 uM (which was used for ITC)

CACHE-HO_1195_43

SPR 110 uM – 28% binding

19F-NMR – does not confirm

Sol/agg ok to 200 uM

3 analogs submitted in round 2.

2 analogs confirm by dose-response SPR.

One tested and does not confirm by 19F-NMR.

CACHE-HO_1195_45

SPR 24 uM – 25% binding

Sol/agg good at 100 uM; trend is strange

Aggregation/solubility measured by DLS

Compound Name	Normalized Intensity (kCnt/s)			Laser Power (%)		
	200µM	100µM	50µM	200µM	100µM	50µM
2% DMSO control	487	827	1595	100	100	100
CACHE-HO_1195_43	1140	1105	566	100	100	100
CACHE-HO_1195_45	1658	910	12881	63	100	100

CACHE 1 – LRRK2_WDR

Participant 1200

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1200_39
 KD LRRK2 101µM – 83% binding
 KD NSD2 – NA – 19% binding
 DSF does not confirm binding
 100% solub /no agg. at 200 µM

36 analogs submitted in round 2.
 Three analogs show dose-response binding in SPR.
 Non confirms in orthogonal method.

CACHE_HO_1200_14
 KD LRRK2 10µM – 27% binding
 solub / agg. Good to 200 µM
 DSF does not confirm binding

CACHE_HO_1200_20
 KD LRRK2 43µM – 20% binding
 ITC – did not confirm
 DSF does not confirm binding
 Solub / agg. Good to 200 µM

CACHE_HO_1200_24
 KD LRRK2 >200uM (520µM) – 52% binding
 solub / agg. Good to 200 µM

CACHE_HO_1200_9
 KD LRRK2 120µM – 14% binding
 solub / agg. Good to 200 µM

Aggregation/solubility measured by DLS

Compound Name	Normalized Intensity (kCnt/s)			Laser Power (%)		
	200µM	100µM	50µM	200µM	100µM	50µM
2% DMSO control	487	827	1595	100	100	100
CACHE-HO_1200_14	1982	1277	973	100	100	100
CACHE-HO_1200_20	1587	953	595	100	100	100
CACHE-HO_1200_24	1260	469	1683	100	100	100
CACHE-HO_1200_9	657	1490	1507	100	100	100

CACHE 1 – LRRK2_WDR

Participant 1201

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1201_96
 KD LRRK2 116 μ M – 44% binding
 KD NSD2 – NA – 44% binding
 100% solub / no agg. at 200 μ M

37 analogs sent in round 2; 5 compounds have measurable KDs.
 DSF: weak stabilization by one analog

Aggregation/solubility measured by DLS

Compound Name	Normalized Intensity (kCnt/s)			Laser Power (%)		
	200 μ M	100 μ M	50 μ M	200 μ M	100 μ M	50 μ M
2% DMSO control	487	827	1595	100	100	100
CACHE-HO_1201_1	424	810	767	100	100	100
CACHE-HO_1201_18	2340	3364	987	78	100	100
CACHE-HO_1201_23	639	1373	773	100	100	100
CACHE-HO_1201_35	1120	663	1545	100	100	100
CACHE-HO_1201_36	1209	1432	1266	90	95	100

CACHE_HO_1201_1
 KD LRRK2 59 μ M – 48% binding
 ITC – does not confirm
 DSF does not confirm
 solub / agg. Good to 200 μ M

CACHE_HO_1201_23
 KD LRRK2 290 μ M – 46% binding
 solub / agg. Ok to 200 μ M
 19F-NMR – does not confirm (ran twice)

CACHE_HO_1201_35
 KD LRRK2 35 μ M – 25% binding
 Solub / agg. Good to 200 μ M

CACHE_HO_1201_36
 KD LRRK2 100 μ M – 36% binding
 Solub up to 200 μ M ok / agg. Good to 200 μ M
 DSF: 0.7C:0.6C at 100;200 μ M

CACHE_HO_1201_18
 KD LRRK2 >200 μ M (335 μ M) – 125% binding
 Sol good to 100 μ M; aggregation compromised at 100 and 200 μ M
 DSF – does not confirm

CACHE 1 – LRRK2_WDR

Participant 1202

CACHE-HO_1202_13/DR002553a
 SPR LRRK2 111 μ M – 30% binding
19F-NMR – confirms binding
 Sol compromised at 200 μ M; agg has a strange trend

Black: 10 μ M compound
 Red: 10 μ M compound +
 20 μ M protein

28 analogs sent in round 2;

5 hits in round 2 with measurable K_D s, of which three have good fit, $K_D \leq 100$ μ M.

One analog shows binding by ¹⁹F-NMR and maybe one by DSF.

CACHE_HO_1202_10
 SPR 106 μ M – 84% binding
 DSF – did not confirm
 Sol ok to 200 μ M; agg compromised from 50 μ M

Aggregation/solubility measured by DLS

Compound Name	Normalized Intensity (kCnt/s)			Laser Power (%)		
	200 μ M	100 μ M	50 μ M	200 μ M	100 μ M	50 μ M
2% DMSO control	487	827	1595	100	100	100
CACHE-HO_1202_10	2886	1318	3887	100	100	100
CACHE-HO_1202_13	6338	1643	1948	65	100	100
CACHE-HO_1202_14	1154	780	914	100	100	100
CACHE-HO_1202_19	1401	857	826	68	100	100
CACHE-HO_1202_22	513	710	1156	100	100	100

CACHE_HO_1202_19
 SPR 88 μ M – 50% binding
 ITC, DSF – did not confirm

CACHE_HO_1202_22
 SPR >200 μ M (410 μ M) – 72% binding
 Sol/agg ok to 100 μ M; but compromised at 200 μ M

PARENT MOLECULES

CACHE_1202_37

SPR LRRK2 23uM – 27% binding

SPR NSD2 – 35% binding

~50% soluble at 200 μM

CACHE_1202_25

SPR LRRK2 144uM – 87% binding

SPR NSD2 177 μM – 163% binding

solub/aggreg OK at 200 μM

CACHE_1202_69

SPR LRRK2 >200uM – 67% binding

solub/aggreg OK at 200 μM

Same compound

CACHE-HO_1202_14

SPR 37 μM – 31% binding

Sol/aggreg ok to 200 uM

DSF: 0.7C at 100 and 200 μM

CACHE 1 – LRRK2_WDR

Participant 1205

PARENT MOLECULES

CACHE_1205_40
 KD LRRK2 35µM – 53% binding
 KD NSD2 – NA – 16% binding

26 analogs of CACHE_1205_93 and 18 analogs of CACHE_1205_40 were submitted in round 2.

Three show dose-response binding by SPR. One appears to thermally stabilize upon binding.

The resupplied hit (CACHE_HO_1205_1) confirms by SPR and 19F-NMR.

Aggregation/solubility measured by DLS

Compound Name	Normalized Intensity (kCnt/s)			Laser Power (%)		
	200µM	100µM	50µM	200µM	100µM	50µM
2% DMSO control	487	827	1595	100	100	100
CACHE-HO_1205_1	1227	619	1195	100	100	100
CACHE-HO_1205_14	1361	995	1564	100	100	100
CACHE-HO_1205_22	898	1583	1489	100	100	100
CACHE-HO_1205_3	632	1257	1093	100	100	100

CACHE-HO_1205_1
 61 uM – 29% binding
19F-NMR – binding confirmed
 Sol/agg good to 200 uM

PARENT MOLECULES

CACHE_1205_93
 KD LRRK2 126µM – 72% binding
 KD NSD2 – NA – 36% binding
 100% solub /no agg. at 200 µM

CACHE_HO_1205_14
 KD LRRK2 290µM – 33% binding
 DSF: seems to weakly stabilize at 200 µM
 Solub /agg. Good to 200 µM

Compound Name	ΔTm	
	200µM	100µM
CACHE-HO_1205_14	0.9	0.5

26 analogs of CACHE_1205_93 and 18 analogs of CACHE_1205_40 were submitted in round 2.

Three show dose-response binding by SPR. One appears to thermally stabilize upon binding.

The resupplied hit (CACHE_HO_1205_1) confirms by SPR and 19F-NMR.

Aggregation/solubility measured by DLS

Compound Name	Normalized Intensity (kCnt/s)			Laser Power (%)		
	200µM	100µM	50µM	200µM	100µM	50µM
2% DMSO control	487	827	1595	100	100	100
CACHE-HO_1205_1	1227	619	1195	100	100	100
CACHE-HO_1205_14	1361	995	1564	100	100	100
CACHE-HO_1205_22	898	1583	1489	100	100	100
CACHE-HO_1205_3	632	1257	1093	100	100	100

CACHE_HO_1205_3
 KD LRRK2 31µM – 17% binding
 ITC: did not confirm
 DSF does not confirm
 Solub / agg. Good to 200 µM

CACHE_HO_1205_22
 KD LRRK2 60µM – 19% binding
 Solub /agg. Good to 200 µM

CACHE 1 – LRRK2_WDR

Participant 1207

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1207_98
 KD LRRK2 22µM – 51% binding
 KD NSD2 – NA – 40% binding
 ~70% solub / agg. at 200 µM

CACHE_HO_1207_46
 KD LRRK2 33µM – 63% binding
 ITC – does not confirm; DSF- does not confirm
 Solub good to 200 µM; agg good to 100 µM

49 analogs were submitted in round 2.

4 analogs show dose-response binding by SPR.

None confirm by DSF

Aggregation/solubility measured by DLS

Compound Name	Normalized Intensity (kCnt/s)			Laser Power (%)		
	200µM	100µM	50µM	200µM	100µM	50µM
2% DMSO control	487	827	1595	100	100	100
CACHE-HO_1207_12	2111	471	604	78	100	100
CACHE-HO_1207_21	442	719	636	100	100	100
CACHE-HO_1207_31	682	1006	523	100	100	100
CACHE-HO_1207_46	3850	1202	969	100	100	100

CACHE_HO_1207_12
 KD LRRK2 52µM – 33% binding
 Solub / agg. Good to 100 µM

CACHE_HO_1207_31
 KD LRRK2 80µM – 24% binding
 DSF- did not confirm
 Solub / agg. Good to 200 µM

CACHE_HO_1207_21
 KD LRRK2 240µM – 57% binding
 DSF – did not confirm
 Solub / agg. Good to 200 µM

CACHE 1 – LRRK2_WDR

Participant 1208

PARENT MOLECULES

CACHE_1208_98
 KD LRRK2 41µM – 115%
 binding
 KD NSD2 – 78 – bad fitting
 BLI – binds in DR
 15% solub / agg. at 200 µM

CACHE_1208_88
 KD LRRK2 137µM – 98% binding
 KD NSD2 – 170µM – 55% binding

46 analogs submitted in round 2.

re-supply of the 2 parent molecules confirmed.

One validated by DSF. But parent binds unrelated target
 NSD2-PWWP1

Aggregation/solubility measured by DLS

Compound Name	Normalized Intensity (kCnt/s)			Laser Power (%)		
	200µM	100µM	50µM	200µM	100µM	50µM
2% DMSO control	487	827	1595	100	100	100
CACHE-HO_1208_49	965	1541	726	100	100	100
CACHE-HO_1208_48	419	711	1021	100	100	100

CACHE_HO_1208_48
 KD LRRK2 82µM – 43% binding
 DSF does not confirm
 Solub / agg. Good to 200 µM

CACHE_HO_1208_49
 KD LRRK2 133µM – 59% binding
DSF stabilization
 Solub / agg. Good to 200 µM

Compound Name	ΔTm	
	200µM	100µM
CACHE-HO_1208_49	2	1.7

PARENT MOLECULES

CACHE_1208_17
KD LRRK2 118 uM – 31% binding
KD NSD2 – 19% binding

9 analogs of 1208_17 were submitted in round 2.

One seemingly unrelated followup shows dose-response binding by SPR (with low % binding).

It does not confirm by 19F-NMR

CACHE-HO_1208_14
KD LRRK2 - 17uM - 23 %
19F-NMR – does not confirm binding
Solubility/ agg good to 200 uM

CACHE-HO_1208_14; LRRK2: 1:1 binding

Percent response

¹⁹F NMR

Black: 10 μM compound
Red: 10 μM compound +
20 μM protein

CACHE 1 – LRRK2_WDR

Participant 1209

CACHE_1209_15
 KD LRRK2 11µM – 37% binding
 KD NSD2 – NA – 31% binding
 100% solub / agg. at 200 µM

CACHE_HO_1209_14
 KD LRRK2 68µM – 45% binding
 DSF – does not confirm; ITC – does not confirm
 Solub/agg. good to 200 µM

CACHE_HO_1209_10
 KD LRRK2 250 – 71% binding
19F-NMR – confirms binding
 Agg may be an issue. Sol is OK

32 analogs submitted in round 2.

Two show orthogonal confirmation by 19F-NMR; One confirms by DSF.

There are some issues with aggregation and solubility for the hits.

Black: 10 µM compound
 Red: 10 µM compound + 20 µM protein

CACHE_HO_1209_41
 KD LRRK2 >200µM (480µM) – 109% binding
 solub / agg. OK to 200 µM
 Resupply of parent molecule

CACHE_HO_1209_1
 KD LRRK2 142µM – 74% binding
DSF – 1C; 1.3C at 100; 200µM
 Solub / agg. good to 200 µM

CACHE_HO_1209_12
 KD LRRK2 110µM – 68% binding
19F-NMR – confirms binding
 Sol good to 100 µM; agg compromised from 50-200 µM

Aggregation/solubility measured by DLS

Compound Name	Normalized Intensity (kCnt/s)			Laser Power (%)		
	200µM	100µM	50µM	200µM	100µM	50µM
2% DMSO control	487	827	1595	100	100	100
CACHE-HO_1209_1	1144	1486	811	100	100	100
CACHE-HO_1209_10	1931	1577	1980	100	100	100
CACHE-HO_1209_12	4286	1769	1846	75	100	100
CACHE-HO_1209_13	598	917	735	100	100	100
CACHE-HO_1209_14	435	941	1241	100	100	100
CACHE-HO_1209_2	917	1781	894	100	100	100
CACHE-HO_1209_22	587	513	668	100	100	100
CACHE-HO_1209_32	1939	552	829	68	100	100
CACHE-HO_1209_41	871	725	1016	100	100	100

CACHE_HO_1209_13
 KD LRRK2 14µM – 18% binding
 Solub / agg. Ok to 200 µM

CACHE_HO_1209_2
 KD LRRK2 19µM – 24% binding
 19F-NMR – no binding
 Solub good to 200 µM;
 aggregation trend is strange

CACHE_HO_1209_32
 KD LRRK2 65µM – 73% binding
 Sol/agg good to 100 µM
 DSF – does not confirm

Compound Name	ΔTm	
	200µM	100µM
CACHE-HO_1209_32	0.4	0.3

19F NMR

Black: 10 µM compound
 Red: 10 µM compound + 20 µM protein

CACHE_HO_1209_22
 KD LRRK2 19µM – 28% binding
 Solub / agg. Ok to 200 µM

PARENT MOLECULEs

CACHE_1209_48
 KD LRRK2 44 μ M – 68% binding
 KD NSD2 – Linear – 53% binding
 70% solub / no agg. at 200 μ M

3 analogs submitted in round 2.

One is resupplied hit that weakly binds in dose-response in SPR.

CACHE-HO_1209_40
 SPR >200uM (310 μ M) – 64% binding
 Sol/agg good to 200 uM

Aggregation/solubility measured by DLS

Compound Name	Normalized Intensity (kCnt/s)			Laser Power (%)		
	200 μ M	100 μ M	50 μ M	200 μ M	100 μ M	50 μ M
2% DMSO control	487	827	1595	100	100	100
CACHE-HO_1209_40	1421	1188	1139	100	100	100

CACHE 1 – LRRK2_WDR

Participant 1210

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1210_69
 KD LRRK2 117µM – 67% binding
 KD NSD2 – NA – 37% binding
 19F-NMR: binds in DR
 100% solub / agg. at 200 µM

Aggregation/solubility measured by DLS

Compound Name	Normalized Intensity (kCnt/s)			Laser Power (%)		
	200µM	100µM	50µM	200µM	100µM	50µM
2% DMSO control	487	827	1595	100	100	100
CACHE-HO_1210_13	1290	1758	1142	100	100	100
CACHE-HO_1210_15	1521	1786	5537	100	100	100
CACHE-HO_1210_2	947	617	841	75	100	100
CACHE-HO_1210_26	1500	1399	1206	100	100	100

CACHE_HO_1210_26
 KD LRRK2 >200µM (500uM); >200% binding
 Sol good to 200 µM

CACHE_HO_1210_13
 KD LRRK2 68µM – 91% binding
 DSF – does not confirm
 Sol OK to 200 uM; agg compromised at 100 and 200 µM

Compound Name	dTm	
	200µM	100µM
CACHE-HO_1210_13	0.1	-0.1

14 round-2 compounds were submitted.
 Four showed dose-response binding by SPR.
 Binding confirmed by 19F-NMR for one.

CACHE_HO_1210_15
 KD LRRK2 71µM – 46% binding
 19F-NMR – **binding confirmed**
 Sol/agg ok to 200 uM

CACHE_HO_1210_2
 KD LRRK2 120µM – 78% binding
 DSF – does not confirm (solubility good to 100 uM); Agg. Good to 200 µM

Compound Name	dTm	
	200µM	100µM
CACHE-HO_1210_2	0.5	0.1

